

Review Article

Life Science: Towards Health and Wealth Generation through Honey Production for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The level of poverty and prevailing poor health of many Nigerians has been a thing of concern to both health practitioners and policy makers. Despite the several poverty-alleviation programmes of successive governments in the country to promote the standard of living among our people, there is ample evidence to show that many Nigerians are still suffering from malnutrition and abject poverty especially in the rural areas. Honey production has however been reported to be a venture that requires little capital investment, but a fast income generator. Honey has also been used worldwide nutritionally and medicinally. In this paper, we reviewed the nutritional value of honey and how its production can bring sustainable income to individual and increase national foreign exchange earning thereby contributing to national development. The problem of adulterated honey was also noted and possible solution suggested.

Keywords: Health, Wealth, Honey, Sustainability, Poverty

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Introduction

In spite of the abundant natural resources of our nation, Nigeria and despite the several poverty-alleviation programmes of successive governments in the country, the level of poverty is still at its peak (Alebiosu, 2003). One of the greatest factors responsible for poverty is unemployment. Unemployment naturally gives rise to poverty and poverty leads to poor health as the purchasing power of someone that is poor is naturally reduced

or completely eroded that one cannot buy those items that can keep one in perfect health. Thus, unemployment, poverty and ill-health are "triplet brothers" that have been the bane of many Nigerians in recent past.

One agro-based venture that is capable of alleviating poverty through self-employment and improvement of the physical health of our people is honey production which is an aspect of beekeeping. Honey production is the management and maintenance of honey bees with a specific objective of producing honey and other honey products (Ayansola, 2003). It is an ancient art that has been in practice for several years in Africa, Europe, North and South America, Australia, Canada and other parts of the world (Lessen, 1967). Honey is a sweet, thick, liquid substance composed mainly of simple sugars produced by honey bees from the nectar of flowers which honey bees collect, transform and combine enzymatically with specific substances of their own, store and leave in the honey comb to mature (Wilson, 2006).

Honey production is a very lucrative and highly profitable venture. It is an enterprise that could rapidly generate income commensurate with capital investment (Ayansola, 2003). It could even be developed towards export-oriented international markets that can earn foreign exchange. Nutritionally, honey is very rich in nutrients. It contains as many as eighty different substances which are very important in human nutrition. Apart from proteins, carbohydrates, organic acids, hormones, anti-microbial and anti-biotic elements, honey contains important vitamins, minerals, trace elements as well as beta-carotene salts (Akachuku, 2001; Alebiosu, 2003; Ayansola, 2003). Honey also contains a small quantity of unknown substances yet to be identified (Brown, 1993). Honey has preventive and curative properties (Bricklin, 1976; Adams, 1977; Kaal, 1991; Ayansola, 2003; Wilson, 2006). Consuming honey in one's diet can therefore improve the health condition of an individual.

In spite of the many economic and nutritional qualities of honey production, the potential of the enterprise has not been appreciably exploited in Nigeria. The apparent low rate of investment is partly due to dearth of information on the potential investment opportunities and the nutritional and industrial value of honey. This paper therefore highlights wealth and health-generating qualities of honey and shows how it can contribute to the sustainable livelihood of rural and urban dwellers in the country. The evil of adulterated (fake) honey is also briefly noted and possible way out of it suggested.

World and African Production of Honey and Bee wax

World production of honey during 1990s was in excess of 1.2 million metric tons (MT) per year (Wilson, 2006). Bee wax production was more than 50,000 MT per year. World demand for these products is substantially in excess of supply of these amounts and is

likely to increase even further in the years ahead. Western Europe and the United States of America are the major importers of these products at an average price of about US \$1,500/MT. World trade in bee wax alone amounted to about 10,000 MT per annum of which Western Europe accounted for about one half of total imports with the world price averaging about US \$4000/MT. In 2004, estimated world production of honey was higher than the medium term average put at 1.38 million/MT while that of bee wax was also higher at 60,153 MT. Production of these products in sub-Saharan Africa (Africa South of the Sahara Excluding the Republic of South Africa) was 135,375 MT of honey and 14,165 MT of bee wax, most of which came from a very few countries (Table 1).

Table 1: Production of honey and bee wax (metric tons) in selected African countries in 2005

Country	Honey	Bee wax
Angola	21,000	2,300
Burundi	240	45
Cameroon	3,000	287
Central African Republic	13,000	690
Chad	960	0
Ethiopia	39,000	4,300
Guinea	600	0
Guinea-Bissau	65	100
Kenya	2,500	2,400
Madagascar	3,930	300
Mali	300	60
Mozambique	390	65
Rwanda	30	21
Reunion	100	0
Senegal	550	77
Sierra Leone	500	110
Sudan	710	175
Tanzania	27,000	1,830
Uganda	300	1,200
Zambia	200	2

Source: Wilson (2006).

African production represents only 9.8 percent of the world production of honey and 23.5 per cent of bee wax. Exports of honey from Sub-Saharan Africa in 2004 were 721 MT valued at US \$224,000 (FAOSTAT data 2005 from internet). These amounts of exports and imports are minimal in world trade figures. They, however, show that African honey is sold on the world market at a price of US \$2,549/MT whereas imports are valued at US \$3098/MT and bee wax is sold at US \$645/MT and bought at US \$878/MT whereas, the

chemical composition of the Nigerian honey compares favourably with imported honey and meets the specifications laid down by the United States Food and Drug Administration (Ayansola, 2003) (Table 2). However, there seem to be considerable opportunities not only for increasing the quantity of Africa's major hive products but also for improving their quality (Wilson, 2006).

Improving Honey Production in Nigeria

Modern beekeeping can help in sustainable production of pure honey. To undertake beekeeping for sustainable honey production, certain basic tools and materials are needed for beehive management, honey harvesting and processing. These include modern hives, smoker, bee suits, bee hat, face veil, hand gloves, honey extractors, was melter and hive tools. All these tools can be sourced locally. In addition to these basic materials, Adekola *et al.*, (2006) had identified a number of factors that are responsible for apicultural non sustainability in the country. These factors include lack of technical know-how, lack of appropriate institutional set-up, poor entrepreneurial, dearth of diversification and adaptive research.

In addition to the above, the following frameworks for sustainable honey production in Nigeria are recommended:

Political Commitment and institutional strengthening

There is a need to sensitize politicians and decision makers to the interrelationship between development, health issues and health nutrition. There is a need for political commitment to enhance environmental health activities, and the integration of health and environmental health activities in national development plans. In this regard, the ministries of health at the three tiers, federal, state and local government environmental protection agencies should be strengthened to face this challenge in honey production.

Community participation

Community participation in honey production and management is crucial for the success of decentralization. Communities can augment available environmental health resources at local level. This is important in terms of provision of basic information regime for honey control and management. It is an important matter for the health services to realize that the self-protection of rural and urban dwellers against adulterated honey is a task which can only be achieved through appropriate attitudinal change towards the available technology which, for the most part, are not the definite of the perfect solutions to the problem to the problem at hand.

Table 2: Chemical composition of some Nigerian and imported honeys

Geographic Source	Vegetation/designation	Colour	Moisture %	Ash %	Glucose %	Fructose %	Sucrose %	Maltose %	Higher sugar %	Diastase activity (arbitrary unit)	Nitrogen %	Free acidity meq/kg	Lactose acidity/kg	Total acidity meq/kg	pH
Nigeria	Cassava	Light amber	23.1	0.00	29.7	33.3	0.90	9.4	2.7	7.3	0.035	7.37	2.72	10.09	4.2
Nigeria	Citrus	Extra-light amber	21.6	0.09	30.5	36.8	1.20	4.3	2.2	15.8	0.037	6.85	1.90	8.75	4.0
Nigeria	Wild	Dark amber	21.0	0.21	26.5	30.0	0.60	1.7	1.3	16.2	0.065	6.05	1.75	7.80	4.3
Greece	Hymettus	Light amber	16.2	0.60	32.4	40.2	1.00	4.1	2.3	8.3	0.065	4.85	0.05	4.90	4.2
Cyprus	Hon Bee	Dark amber	23.5	0.24	30.4	36.4	1.90	6.9	0.9	4.1	0.358	6.10	1.15	7.25	4.3
UK	Pure	Light	23.5	0.20	31.4	35.1	1.90	7.0	1.1	13.0	0.107	5.20	0.65	5.65	4.3

Source: Adapted from Ikediobi *et al.*, 1985

Wealth-Generating Potential of Honey Production

Collins (1984) defines wealth as much money or property, riches, the state of being rich a large amount, abundance, valuable products, contents or derivatives, everything that has value in money or price. Wealth generation, on the other hand, is all about development economics (Ogundele, 2004). In fact, the very concept of wealth generation and modernization represent implicit as well as explicit value premises about desirable goals for achieving, what Mahatma Gandhi once called “realization of the human potential” (Todaro and Smith, 2003). Honey production is such an agro-based enterprise that can empower a honey producer to be a wealth-generator and thereby realize his God-given human potential.

Honey Production as an Enterprise

Honey production is of considerable importance in the economies of both developed and underdeveloped countries. It gives a profitable and healthy form of livelihood to a large number of people. Beekeeping is the only agricultural business that offers the best promise of maximum income from a minimum of input of capital and labour (Ayansola, 2003). This is because bees do not require daily attention and maintenance cost. Also, beekeeping requires no vast areas of land and does not interfere with other occupational engagements. Thus, beekeeping can be perfectly integrated into other natural resources management.

In terms of job creation, any other thing can hardly surpass the honeybee resource. According to Ayansola (2003), in the USA, there are over 212,000 beekeepers. Besides, beekeeping generates jobs for million other people in ancillary businesses like research, bee breeding, laboratory services, training and consultancy, honey packing, candle making, cosmetic production, api-therapy, honey boards and beekeeping equipment manufacturing. Also, beekeeping does not generate waste but wealth. Unlike the case with other vocations, all the products of beekeeping – honey, bee wax, pollen, royal jelly, propolis and bee venom – have commercial value. Profit for first year of investment in beekeeping and honey production can be as high as 96.5% over cost of production while that of second year can also be as high as 97.5%. Thus, beekeeping is one of the most feasible means to create wealth and alleviate poverty.

Honey as a Foreign Exchange Depletor

As a foreign exchange depletor, the demand for honey often exceeds supply hence the nation Nigeria spends parts of her hard earned exchange earnings on the importation of honey and other honey products (Akachuku, 2001). This is because, in the last three

decades, availability of pure honey in local markets and along road-sides had declined. This is as a result of deforestation resulting from over exploitation of the forest productions as well as other factors identified by Adekola *et al.*, (2006) that cause non sustainability in apiculture in the country.

Honey Production as an Exchange Earner

If produced on large-scale, honey can be exported and thereby improve national economy. Ayansola (2003) remarked that beekeeping is now known to bring fortune to nations as it contributes significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of many countries which include the four largest producers of honey, namely, the United States of America, Mexico, Argentina and Australia. In Australia, honey is tagged “liquid gold” because of its contribution to the national treasury. Other major producers are China, Israel, Canada and Brazil. In Africa, recognized producers are indicated in Table 1. However, Tanzania is the world largest exporter of bee wax. In all these countries, honey industry is so vital that national boards exist to oversee activities within the industry with a view to protecting the interest of beekeepers. However, beekeeping and commercialization in Nigeria has not been appreciably exploited. Certainly, this is a goldmine” that is yet to be mined!

Health - Generating Quality of Honey

Increased productivity by individual in all sectors of the economy depends on the good health condition of the labour force (Adeniyi, 2004). The impact of poor health on productivity has been well documented in the literature. For instance, Adeniyi (2004) observed that the health of the population is a very important fact in determining the volume of output of goods and services which a country achieves from the productive resources at its disposal. Economic growth of any country certainly depends critically on a healthy and well - nourished population. Therefore, the capacity for productive work is adversely affected when the population suffers from debilitating disease and malnutrition.

Unfortunately, most developing countries of the world, and particularly Africa, face various health problems unlike the developed countries (Ajala *et al.*, 2001). Such diseases like cholera, malaria and diarrhea, which are environmentally related, are common in Africa. Other diseases that are ravaging Africa are nutrition - based. For instance, the quality of refined sugar being imported and consumed in the continent annually is overwhelmingly large. However, when eaten, refined sugar drains and leaches the body of precious vitamins and minerals because of the demand its digestion, detoxification and elimination make upon one’s entire system, thus impairing the health. No wonder, then,

that in the 1950s Dr. William Coda Martin called refined sugar a poison (Ajala *et al.*, 2001). But quite unlike refined sugar, when starches and complex sugars (like that in honey) are taken and digested, they are broken down into simple sugars called “monosaccharide”, which are usable substances. That is today, eating refined sugar gives poison while eating honey gives nutrients. There is therefore the need to step up production of honey in Nigeria for a large percentage of our people to eat at affordable price. Also, there is a need to re-orientate our people to change their ‘taste bud’ from refined sugar to honey as sweetener, letting them know the concealed danger in eating refined sugar. By doing this, the health of our people will be greatly enhanced for economic growth.

Chemical Composition of Honey

The chemical composition of honey varies according to the type of flower, soil and atmospheric conditions, especially moisture (Ayansola, 2003). Also, the colour, aroma, flavours and thickness of honey vary according to the nectar and pollen of flowers while its viscosity is normally influenced by season, temperature, relative humidity and time of harvesting. However, variation in the honey viscosity does not affect its quality. The following substances have been found in honey: Vitamins (e.g. thiamine – Vit B1, ascorbic acid – Vit C, folic acid. Riboflavin, pyridoxine, panthothenic acid, Vitamins B2, B3, B5, C4, D and K, proteins e.g. albuminoid and various amino acids) and complex sugars (e. g. maltose, sucrose, lactose, glucose and fructose), minerals (e. g. Al, Ca, Cl, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mg, P, K, Si and Na). The quantity of these substances varies from location to location depending on the type of nectar – producing plants available. Honey also contains a small quantity of unknown substances yet to be identified (Brown, 1993). Table 3 shows the proximate analysis of two honey samples using two types of bee hives.

Characteristics of Honey

The characteristics of a given sample of honey affect its nutritional and curative properties. The characteristics of honey are as follows:

- (i) **Acidity:** Honey destroys bacteria or germs (anti-bacterial property) because of its acidic nature. The main acids found in honey are malic, citric, tannic and succinic. The acids are responsible for the stability of honey in storage against germs of micro-organisms such as bacteria. According to Akachuku (2001), the acid content accounts for about 0.5% of the dry weight of honey. Although honey has an acid reaction of pH 3.29 – 4.87, it is potentially an alkaline food.
- (ii) **Enzyme content:** Pure honey contains the following enzymes – amylase, invertase, catalase, oxidase and phosphatase. The enzymes enhance chemical changes especially in the digestion of food. They also make honey very inhospitable and unsuitable for the growth of harmful micro-organisms or germs.

- (iii) **Hygroscopicity:** Honey is generally hygroscopic and draws moisture from the atmosphere when exposed or uncovered. Pure honey maintains moisture content of 11 - 21%. When it is exposed, it however draws more moisture from the atmosphere or from the surrounding air and become relatively diluted. Honey has unlimited power to draw moisture from germs and hence dehydrates germs to render them harmless.

Table 3: Proximate analysis of honey samples from modern beekeeping hives in South-Eastern Nigeria.

Nutrient Composition	Honey Samples	
	Langstroth Hive	Kenya Top Bar Hive
Moisture content (%)	19.25	19.75
Dry matter (%)	90.75	80.25
Carbohydrate (%)	93.93	93.43
Crude Protein (%)	1.94	1.94
Total ash (%)	0.25	0.25
Fats and Oil (%)	3.99	4.38
Maltose (%)	8.45	8.60
Sucrose (%)	2.20	2.50
Lactose (%)	1.45	1.55
Fructose (%)	0.95	0.88
K ⁺	0.04	0.02
Na ⁺	0.07	0.02
Ca ⁺⁺	0.29	0.28
M ⁺⁺	0.10	0.07
P	0.04	0.05
N	0.31	0.31
Calorific Value (kj)	418.90	420.90

Source: Akachuku, (1996)

Honey as an Improver of Health and Curer of Diseases

Pure honey, apart from being used as sweetener in food, also has curative properties. The value and importance of honey has been underestimated in the past due to lack of awareness and information on its medicinal properties. Honey in its natural state is generally used to guard against illness, treat certain ailments and improve bodily

functions. For example, honeybee helps in the prevention of vomiting and improves appetite in pregnant women. Honey encourages growth in premature babies, acts as a dietary aid in metabolic disorders and can serve as supplementary food when breastfeeding is insufficient for a child (Kaal, 1991). Honey stabilizes blood pressure and regulates heartbeats.

Honey can be used as food directly to build up the body, promote growth, and acts as a buffer to maintain acid – base balance of the body. It is known to give vitality, good health and long life to people who take honey on a regular basis. Beekeepers are known to have a longer life span (Ayansola, 2003). Adams (1977) and Bricklin (1976) cited many reported cases of how honey miraculously healed skin burns and diseases which include severe burns, gangrene of the foot, chickenpox, carbuncle, and ulcerated legs from varicose veins. Honey, applied topically, has been able to cure these diseases. Besides, concentrated sucrose in honey kills bacteria, thus making honey an excellent germ-killer. Honey is also used in moisturizing and enriching cosmetic creams and in pharmaceutical preparations that are applied directly to open wounds, sores, ulcers and burns as well as being useful for assisting tissue (re)-generation and reduction of scars due to various types of wounds (Wilson, 2006).

Identification of pure honey

Pure honey is a natural sugar that requires no digestion and is thus easily assimilated. But honey can be adulterated by adding sugar cane syrup, starch, gum, wheat flour and so on to increase its volume and/or viscosity as to make illicit gains. Adulterated honey is otherwise known as fake honey (Ayansola, 2003). To avoid adulterated honey, it is necessary to know how to distinguish original natural honey from fake one. The common effective methods of identification of pure honey include the following:

- (i) Take a stick of matches and insert it into the honey, then strike it on the box. If it fires, it is pure honey, if not, it is impure or adulterated.
- (ii) Add some quantity of honey to a cup containing clean water. Original honey will go down to the bottom of the cup and leave clear water on top. It will require some effort to use a spoon to mix the honey with water by stirring. When mixed, it mixes totally and leaves no particles at the bottom of the cup. Adulterated honey will do the opposite of the above exercises.

There is therefore a need to re-orientate both the Federal and State Ministries of Health to their new role in pure honey processing and management in rural and urban areas of the country. Honey production management should be seen as a necessary service which

must be adequately funded to achieve success and create an environment for honey production and sustainable commercial beekeeping in the country.

As for the detection of adulterated honey, it is recommended that the Federal Government do the following:

- (i) Equip health personnel to acquire necessary skills to deal with the problem.
- (ii) Create a flexible geo-reference database for the documentation of types and extent of adulterated honey in Nigerian cities. Such data can also be used to identify areas where adulterated honey are produced and sold to the people for research purpose and public enlightenment.
- (iii) Legislate against naïve, dangerous and adulterated honey methods.

The above steps against honey adulteration are necessary and urgent because if fake (adulterated) honey is taken, it can cause serious and undesirable side-effects on the health of the users. Thus, adulterated honey cannot generate good health but instead undermines it. Again, adulterated honey, if exported, can affect the economy and image of the country adversely, thus undermining the capacity of honey as a potential and serious foreign exchange earner. We however believe that whenever Honey Management Council of Nigeria is established by the Federal Government, it will be in a position to squarely deal with the problem of adulterated honey.

Conclusion

The importance of pure honey either as an income-generator, foreign exchange earner or health-improver cannot be overemphasized or well managed for efficiency in productive activities. Unfortunately, honey production has not been appreciably exploited to realize its perceived potential in Nigeria. Besides, adulteration of honey constitutes a great threat to the honey industry as the use of adulterated honey undermines the economy as well as the health of the user. This paper concludes that honey production industry should be given its rightful position in the national economy and the issues of adulteration settled in view of the industry's potential as a wealth-generator and health-improver. The issues considered important are good governance, community participation and appropriate technology among others.

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